

EFFECT OF DOMESTIC PROCESSING (COOKING AND ROASTING) ON ANTIOXIDANT POTENTIAL OF BAMBARA GROUNDNUT EXTRACT (*VIGNA SUBTERANEA* L.VERDC.)

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ABSTRACT

Bambara groundnut is a crop that is considered to be indigenous to the African continent. Bambara groundnut is grown mainly for its edible and nutritionally rich seeds. The aim of this study was to explore the effect of domestic processing on the antioxidant potential of Bambara groundnut. Two landraces from Yobe and Kano states, Nigeria were screened in raw and processed forms. The effect of cooking and roasting on antioxidant potentials and phenolic phytochemicals of the two landraces were assessed. The study employed *in vitro* antioxidant assays 1-1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) and Ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP) to screen for change in antioxidant property and Folin Ciocalteu assay to screen for change in phenolic content respectively. Result were presented in mean \pm SD. The Yobe landrace exhibited the highest DPPH free radical scavenging activity with $56.58\% \pm 0.05$ for the roasted Bambara compared to $40.57\% \pm 0.08$ of the Kano landrace. Again the ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP) was higher in the roasted Yobe landrace of Bambara groundnut with $9.40 \text{ mmol Fe}^{2+}/100\text{g} \pm 0.40$ compared to $8.34 \text{ mmol Fe}^{2+}/100\text{g} \pm 0.36$ in the roasted Kano Bambara groundnut. The total phenolic content were $34.22 \text{ as GAE} \pm 0.111$ and $28.19 \pm 0.25 \text{ as GAE}$ in the roasted Yobe and roasted Kano Bambara groundnut respectively. The effect of domestic processing on the antioxidant activity and total phenolic content follows the same trend and the increase was revealed in the following order: RBY>RBK>CBY>CBK>CSY>CSK.

Keywords: Bambara Groundnut, landrace, domestic cooking, domestic roasting

INTRODUCTION

Bambara groundnut (*Vigna subterranea*) is a legume with *subterranea* fruit set and is cultivated by small farm holders over much of semiarid Africa (Azam-Ali, 1993). The production of Bambara groundnut Africa-wide has been recorded to be approximately 0.3 million tonnes annually (Hillocks *et al.*, 2012; Nedumaran *et al.*, 2015) with Nigeria regarded as the largest producer of Bambara groundnut in Africa (0.1 million tonnes per annum (Hillocks *et al.*, 2012). However Bambara groundnut is still among the underutilized legume in Nigeria (Abiodun and Adepeju, 2011). Bambara groundnut has not been adequately exploited as human food because of constraints like hard to cook phenomenon, strong beany

flavour, as well as the presence of anti-nutrients, poor dehulling and milling characteristics (Enwere and Hung, 1996, Abiodun and Adepeju, 2011). In Nigeria, Bambara groundnut is processed through various techniques like boiling, roasting, and frying. In south eastern Nigeria, dried Bambara groundnut seeds are made into paste and used in the preparation of steamed products, such as “Okpa” (Bamishaiye *et al.*, 2011). Texturized plant protein is an excellent meat substitute in many dishes and they approximate the aesthetic qualities (primarily texture, flavour and appearance), and low chemical characteristics of specific types of meat. Thus, Bambara groundnut can be used quite freely to replace the high priced lumps of meat for adequate nutrition (Okonkwo and Okpara, 2010).

A number of food grains have been reported in literature to possess antioxidant activities that may be beneficial to health (Cardador-Martínez *et al.*, 2002; Winter, 2009). Traditional medicinal uses in some communities where Bambara groundnuts are grown suggest that they may possess some nutraceutical properties. Karikari *et al.* (1995) reported that the seeds of the mature black Bambara groundnut landrace are used in traditional medicine in Botswana. According to Swanevelder (1995), chewing and swallowing raw Bambara groundnut was reported to check nausea and vomiting, a remedy that is often used to treat morning sickness in pregnant women. Despite the reported medicinal uses of Bambara groundnuts, there is limited experimental evidence to suggest that they possess nutraceutical properties or exhibit some form of bioactivity. However, Nyau (2015) reported that Bambara groundnut extract has ferric reducing antioxidant activity that is comparable to commonly consumed legumes such as lentils, common beans and chickpea. Exploring underutilized legume resources is of great significance taking into account their rich nutraceutical value (Bhat and Karim, 2009).

Different processing techniques used conventionally have varied effects on nutrients and their bioavailability. Heat processing affects concentration of phytochemicals, antioxidant activity and nutritional value of food (Sreeramulu *et al.*, 2013). Since domestic cooking and roasting are the common ways by which legumes are prepared for consumption, therefore, investigating their effects on antioxidant property and phenolic content of Bambara groundnuts will go a long way to establish their potentials for

use in the functional foods and nutraceutical industry. Additionally this information is necessary for strategies aimed at promoting the consumption of Bambara groundnuts by the populace, thereby decreasing the prevalence of malnutrition in Nigeria and particularly in the north where it is prevalent. This study was conducted to explore the effect of domestic processing on antioxidant potential of Bambara groundnut.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Folin-Ciocalteu's phenol reagent, 1, 1-Diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH), Gallic acid were obtained from Sigma chemical co. (St Louis, MO, USA). All other chemicals/reagents and solvent used were of analytical grade.

Sample Collection

Two different landraces of Bambara groundnut were purchased at Dawanau Grain Market Dawakin Tofa local Government Area, Kano state and at Potiskum grain market, Yobe state respectively. The Yobe Bambara groundnut landrace was a cream variety while the Kano Bambara groundnut landrace was brown and mottled variety.

Determination of antioxidant potentials of Bambara groundnut extract

The antioxidant potentials of both two different Bambara groundnut landraces were determined. The determination was done for the processed and the unprocessed Bambara groundnut.

Raw (Unprocessed) Bambara groundnut

Fresh Bambara groundnut seeds were thoroughly cleaned and foreign materials as well as broken and immature seeds were removed. The clean seeds were shade-dried for three consecutive days to a constant weight at room temperature. The dry seeds were then pulverized to fine powder and stored in an air-tight container in a refrigerator until used.

Cooking

A set of Bambara groundnut seeds was cooked in water in a seed to water ratio of 1:10 (w/v) at (100°C) for 3 hrs 48 min. as practiced by the locals. After cooking, the water was drained off and the cooked seeds were mashed into a paste using a ceramic mortar and then stored in an air-tight container in refrigerator until used.

Roasting

Another set of the Bambara groundnut seeds were placed on a frying pan and then roasted using firewood with a temperature at about 300°C for about 1 hr as practiced by the locals. Thereafter, the roasted seeds were pulverized to powder and then stored in an air-tight container in a refrigerator until used. The samples were labeled as follows: Cooked Bambara groundnut Yobe landrace (CBK), Roasted Bambara groundnut Yobe landrace (RBY), Cooked Bambara groundnut Kano landrace (CBK), Roasted Bambara groundnut Kano landrace (RBK), Raw Bambara Yobe landrace (CSY), Raw Bambara groundnut Kano landrace (CSK).

Extract Preparation

Acidified 80% methanol (with 0.1% HCL) was employed for extraction of phytochemicals from the cooked and roasted Bambara groundnut. 50g of each seed powder was soaked in 500ml of acidified methanol (0.1% Hcl) the mixture was allowed to stand for two days, the mixture was then filtered with whatman no 1 filter paper and the filtrate was evaporated using water bath at 40-50°C to obtain the dry extract. The dry extract was then stored in dark until use.

Estimation of DPPH Scavenging Activity

DPPH (1-1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl) radical scavenging activity was determined according to (Yu *et al.*, 2002). This method is based on the ability of the antioxidant to scavenge the DPPH cationic radical. To 1 mg/ml of sample extract, 2.0 ml of DPPH reagent (0.1 mM in methanol) was added and vortexed vigorously. This was allowed to stand in dark for 45min at room temperature, and the discoloration of

DPPH was measured against a suitable blank (containing all the reagent except the sample extract) at 517 nm. Lower absorbance represents a high DPPH scavenging activity.

$$\% \text{scavenging activity} = \left[1 - \left(\frac{A_{\text{sample}}}{A_{\text{control}}} \right) \right] \times 100$$

Where A_{control} and A_{sample} are the absorbance values at 517 nm of the control and the sample extract, respectively.

Total Phenolic Content

Soluble and hydrolysable phenolic contents (free phenols) were estimated as described by (Singh *et al.*, 2002; Singleton and Rossi, 1965 using the Folin–Ciocalteu reagent. For each extract, a 1.0 ml aliquot was placed into a 50 ml volumetric flask, and the extract was mixed with 30 ml deionized water, 2.5 ml of Folin– Ciocalteu reagent, and 7.5 ml of 20% Na_2CO_3 solution. The final volume of the mixture was adjusted to 50 ml using distilled water. After incubation for 30 min at room temperature, absorbance of the mixture was measured at 765 nm, with distilled water as the blank. The total phenolic content of each extract was determined from the standard curve based on gallic acid; the content was expressed in mg of gallic acid equivalents (GAE) per gram of legume (mg/g).

FRAP Assay

The ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP) was assessed using the Prussian blue method described by Oyaizu (1986). To measure the total reducing power of the test samples, each extract (2 ml) was mixed in a test tube with 2.0 ml of 0.5 mol/l phosphate buffer (PBS, pH 6.6) containing 2.0 ml of 1% $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ solution. The mixtures were incubated at 50°C for 20 min. After the addition of 2.0 ml 10% trichloroacetic acid, each mixture was centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 min. The supernatant (2.5 ml) was collected and mixed with 2.5 ml of deionized water containing 0.5 ml of 0.1% ferric chloride. The absorbance was measured at 700 nm using a spectrophotometer, with distilled water as the blank. Increasing absorbance indicates high reducing ability of the extract.

Data Analysis

All measurements were performed in triplicate. Experimental results were expressed as Mean \pm SD.

Analysis of variance was done using Microsoft 2013 $p < 0.05$ was considered statically significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The total phenolic content of Bambara groundnut (Yobe and Kano landraces) under different processing conditions is shown in Table 1. Both Bambara groundnut landraces showed increase in phenolic content upon cooking and roasting. But roasting significantly increased the phenolic content ($P < 0.05$). The order of the increase in TPC was $\text{RBY} > \text{RBK} > \text{CBY} > \text{CBK} > \text{CSY} > \text{CSK}$.

Table 1: Total Phenolic content (mg of Gallic Acid Equivalent/g) of two Bambara Groundnut Landraces in comparison with the Unprocessed (control)

Processing methods	Yobe	Kano
Raw Bambara	21.44 \pm 0.40 ^a	19.45 \pm 0.49 ^a
Roasted Bambara	34.22 \pm 0.11 ^b	28.19 \pm 0.25 ^b
Cooked Bambara	26.47 \pm 0.02 ^c	21.62 \pm 0.33 ^c

Results are expressed as mean \pm SD of three independent experiments; values with same superscript across rows are significantly different ($P < 0.05$) and values with different superscript down the columns are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

Phenolic compounds are widely distributed in the plant kingdom and are important in the antioxidant capacity of plant *in vitro* due to their ability to donate proton and form stable radical intermediates (Scalbert *et al*, 2005). Phenolic compounds present in leguminous plant acts as radical scavengers, reducing agents and chelators of metal ions. Total phenolic content (TPC) by follin ciocalteu reagent and *in vitro* antioxidant assays (DPPH and FRAP) represent convenient methods for the determination of

potential sources of antioxidant compounds (Stratil *et al.*, 2006, Mishra *et al.*, 2014). Antioxidant compounds have significant potential health benefit ranging from protection of cellular constituents against oxidative damage thereby limiting the risk of various degenerative diseases associated with oxidative stress such as cancer, cardiovascular diseases and osteoporosis.

The total phenolic content of Bambara groundnut Kano and Yobe landraces extracted after different processing conditions are shown in Table 1. Both extracts showed significant increase in phenolic content upon cooking and roasting, but the latter increased the phenolic content to a higher extent. This could be due to the leaching of some of the phenolic compounds into the water during cooking (Xu and Chang, 2008).

The result of ferric reducing antioxidant power of Bambara groundnut is presented in Table 2 the processed Bambara groundnut had higher FRAP values than the unprocessed Bambara groundnut types. The results showed that the Yobe landrace had higher ferric reducing ability than the Kano landrace and the difference was significant ($P < 0.05$).

Table 2: FRAP (Ferric ion Reducing Antioxidant Power) (mmol Fe²⁺/100g) of the two (2) Bambara Groundnut Landraces in Comparison with the Unprocessed (control).

Processing method	Yobe	Kano
Raw Bambara	6.66 ± 0.27 ^a	5.79 ± 0.15 ^a
Roasted Bambara	9.40 ± 0.26 ^b	8.34 ± 0.36 ^b
Cooked Bambara	7.37 ± 0.04 ^c	6.54 ± 0.11 ^c

Results are expressed in means ± SD of three independent experiment; values with same superscript across rows are significantly different ($P < 0.05$) and values with different superscript down the column are significantly different ($p < 0.05$)

The DPPH scavenging activity of the raw and cooked Bambara groundnut is presented in Table 3 the results shows that domestic processing significantly ($P < 0.05$) improves the DPPH activity of Bambara

groundnut. The result indicated that the Yobe landrace has significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher DDPH scavenging activity compared with the Kano landrace.

Table: 3: DPPH (1, 1-Diphenyl-2-picryl-hydrazyl) Scavenging Activity (%) of the two (2) Bambara landraces in comparison with the raw type (control).

Processing methods	Yobe	Kano
Raw Bambara	44.34 ± 0.24 ^a	30.27 ± 0.07 ^a
Roasted Bambara	56.58 ± 0.05 ^b	40.57 ± 0.08 ^b
Cooked Bambara	50.49 ± 0.34 ^c	38.00 ± 0.59 ^c

Results are express in means ± SD of three independent experiment; values with the same superscript across columns are significantly different (P<0.05) and values with different superscript down the column are significantly different (p<0.05).

Effect of Domestic Processing on Phenolic Content of Bambara Groundnut

The difference in TPC between the two Bambara groundnut landrace could be attributed to genetic factors and variation between cultivars (Amarowicz and Pegg, 2008),genetic and growing factor (environment condition) have been reported to affect the concentration of TPC hence the antioxidant activity of the legume extract (Rocha *et al.*, 2007 and Acar *et al.*, 2009). The increase in TPC during thermal processing has been reported by other researchers (Boateng *et al.*, 2008, Duenas *et al.*, 2009; Fernandez *et al.*, 2006). Mishra *et al.* (2014) also reported that thermal processing (cooking and roasting) increased the TPC of red rice significantly. According to the result obtained thermal processing increased the free phenolics of Bambara groundnut. The results of these studies are in agreement with similar studies carried out using other types of seeds (Dewanto *et al.*, 2002, Chandrasekara and Shahidi 2011). Carciochi *et al.* (2016) showed that roasting above 190° C for 90mins increased the TPC of quinoa seeds by 18-60% compared to its raw counterpart. In another study heat treatment at 120°c for 30min increased about 100% TPC levels in barley seeds (Gallegos-infante *et al.*, 2010).

The observed increase may be due to leaching of some of the phenolic compounds into the water during cooking (Xu and Chang, 2008). This could be explained considering the fact that phenolic compounds originally bounded in the seed matrix by glycosylation/estrification could be released as a result of

roasting or cooking, making them more soluble in the extraction solvent (Dewanto *et al.*, 2002, Shahidi 2011, Carciochi *et al.*, 2016). The Yobe landrace has higher antioxidant activities and phenolic contents compared to the Kano landrace. These findings have demonstrated that Bambara groundnuts have the potential for use in the nutraceutical industry. Based on this, it is suggested that consumption of Bambara groundnuts could possibly offer some health benefits since they contain phytochemicals that have been reported to possess protective functions. Consumption of Bambara groundnuts can be as good as other commonly consumed legumes and this is an opportunity for dietary and crop diversification on the part of the consumers and farmers respectively.

The Effect of Domestic Processing on DPPH and FRAP of Bambara Groundnut

The nutraceutical potentials of legumes is usually determined by the total phenolic content that exhibit antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and anticancer properties (Chon, 2012, Swieca and Baroniak, 2014a, 2014b). High temperature (100-300°C) can increase phenolic content, hence the antioxidant activity, which could be because solvent viscosity decreases and movement of molecules is accelerated, leading to the dissolution of polyphenol and an increased in diffusion coefficient and stability (Ajila *et al.*, 2011). The higher antioxidant properties of the roasted Bambara groundnut may be due to the presence of higher TPC in the roasted Bambara groundnut, since percentage DPPH inhibition is directly correlated with TPC (Alothman *et al.*, 2009). Nicoli *et al.* (1997) shows increase in DPPH scavenging activity during roasting of coffee brews and also by Rocha *et al.* (2007) during pressure cooking of common beans. Differences in the concentration of phenolic compounds and the antioxidant potentials of the two different landraces of Bambara groundnut could be as a result of factors such as variety, growing (harvesting) and storage conditions (Hakinen and Torren, 2000; Nintali and Bacchiocca, 2003; Nyau, 2013). There is a possibility that the emergent compounds have good free radical scavenging abilities. Therefore Bambara groundnut has the potentials for use as nutraceuticals and their consumption could possibly offer some health benefits.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the study has demonstrated that cooking and roasting has positive effects on the antioxidant activities and phenolic Phytochemicals of Bambara groundnuts. In both landraces Bambara groundnuts, antioxidant activities are higher in the processed samples compared to the unprocessed. Domestic processing favoured the release of phenolic compounds and subsequently resulted in high antioxidant activity. Domestic processing therefore enhances the nutraceutical profiles in both landraces of Bambara Groundnuts. The antioxidant activities of both the processed Yobe and Kano Bambara groundnuts were higher compared to the unprocessed. Changes in the antioxidant activities are positive and may be attributed to the increase in the concentrations of total phenolic compounds. Further, the increase in the speed of DPPH free radical scavenging reaction by the antioxidants in the processed Bambara groundnut may be attributed to the new emerging compounds. These findings have demonstrated that Bambara groundnuts have the potential for use in the nutraceutical industry. Based on this, it is suggested that consumption of Bambara groundnuts could possibly offer some health benefits since they contain Phytochemicals constituents that have been reported to possess protective functions. Consumption of Bambara groundnuts can be as good as other commonly consumed legumes and this is an opportunity for dietary and crop diversification on the part of the consumers and farmers respectively.

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